

Colour Reaction of Diphenylamine with Aldehydes

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Manuscript received 3 August 1979, revised 28 March 1980, accepted 9 July 1980

Diphenylamine reacts with aldehydes in acidic solutions. Diphenylamine salts (hydrochloride, sulphate and perchlorate) react with aldehydes directly. These reactions may be divided into two classes; the first is based on formation of very stable ternary iminium salts, and the second class depends on the formation of highly unstable and deliquescent ternary iminium salts. Latter salts are autoxidized with atmospheric oxygen to give a deeply coloured compound which can be used for the sensitive colorimetric detection and determination. The ternary iminium perchlorate obtained may be used as explosives.

DIPHENYLAMINE is an important analytical reagent. It has been used in many oxidation reduction titrations¹. It has been used as a chromogenic reagent in the detection and determination of aldehydes^{2,3,4}, sugars^{5,6} vanadium^{7,8} etc. Qureshi *et al*⁹ have published a sensitive and selective resin spot test for diphenylamine. For this test the limit of identification was found to be 0.25 μg in a limiting dilution of $1:2 \times 10^4$. The test is based upon the reaction of diphenylamine with *p*-dimethylamino-benzaldehyde in the presence of hydrochloric acid. In this reaction they have noted that a yellow colour is formed which on heating turns green or bluish green. The coloured products obtained from the reactions of diphenylamine with sugars have been studied by Mamose *et al*^{5,6}. Recently⁴ diphenylamine has been used as a general reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of aromatic aldehydes. Aromatic aldehydes and some of their binary mixtures can be determined. The maximum error was found to be ± 6 and $\pm 10\%$ for single and for simultaneous determination of aldehydes respectively. However, the isolation and identification of diphenylamine-aldehydes reaction products have been found to be difficult and it has not been reported so far.

Now an attempt is made to isolate and identify the coloured products of these reactions. The results obtained are discussed below. Diphenylamine reacts with aldehydes in acidic solutions. Its salts (hydrochloride, sulphate and perchlorate) react with aldehydes directly. These reactions may be divided in two classes. The first is based on the formation of a very stable ternary iminium salt as it is found in the case of cinnamaldehyde and its derivatives. To 2.7 gm (0.01 mole) of diphenylamine perchlorate solution in ethanol (20 ml) in a conical flask was added 2.6 ml (0.02 mole) of 97% cinnamaldehyde. On swirling, crystals separated with the evolution of heat. The crystals were filtered, washed with ether and recrystallized from acetonitrile. The yield was high (90%). The

product has m.p. 195°. The following structure may be proposed for this product, N-cinnamyldene-diphenyliminium perchlorate.

The following are the evidences in support of the above structure. The presence of chlorine in compound (R) was found to be positive. An explosive cracking on heating (R) indicates the presence of perchlorate ion. The acidic solution of (R) hydrolysis on adding water in excess indicate the presence of $\text{>C}=\overset{\text{+}}{\text{N}}\text{<}$. The elemental analysis results are the following:

		C	H	N
Per cent	Found	65.40	4.69	3.74
	Calculated	65.70	4.70	3.60

I.R. analysis by KBr method shows the absence of >NH and >C=O bands and the presence of a new strong absorption band at 1660 cm^{-1} indicative of $\text{>C}=\overset{\text{+}}{\text{N}}\text{<}$. The N.M.R. spectra consisted of signals occurring at $\delta = 9.1$ (J=10Hz, d,A), $\delta = 8.26$ (J=15Hz, d,B), $\delta = 7.50$ (s,C) and $\delta = 7.03$ (J=10.74, q,D) in trifluoroacetic acid at 60MHz Varian. Signal at $\delta = 7.50$ consists of a shoulder at $\delta = 7.65$; it may be due to the fact that two of the phenyl groups are attached to $\overset{\text{+}}{\text{N}}$. The assignments are made as shown in compound (R). N.M.R. data for ternary iminium salts have been discussed in detail by Leonard *et al*⁹. U.V. spectrum in methanol consists of a strong absorption band indicative of $\text{>C}=\overset{\text{+}}{\text{N}}\text{<}$ at 283 nm. E.P.R.

spectrum shows no signals. The X-ray data obtained (Table 1) show that this is a new compound. Similar compounds have been isolated and identified by Leonard *et al*⁹. Ternary iminium salts obtained in this class are very stable in air. Like other organic perchlorates they may be suitable for using as explosives¹⁰. They may also be used in synthetic chemistry because they are very prone to nucleophilic⁹ attack.

TABLE 1—X-RAY DATA FOR N-CINNAMYLDIENEDIPHENYLIMINIUM PERCHLORATE

d values	I/I ₀	d values	I/I ₀
12.989	9	2.832	8
9.817	14	2.794	11
9.017	30	2.761	12
7.019	13	2.696	6
6.804	13	2.619	12
6.320	14	2.493	5
6.032	19	2.372	7
5.467	10	2.330	5
4.951	42	2.231	6
4.766	40	2.102	6
4.571	53	2.013	5
4.480	43	1.458	95
4.267	48	1.451	23
4.111	35	1.414	15
4.037	39	1.403	15
3.863	36	1.392	86
3.767	51	1.383	95
3.705	32	1.362	100
3.559	20	1.353	99
3.424	16	1.323	95
3.299	16	1.320	74
2.252	12	1.317	95
3.076	14	1.310	60
2.976	15	1.304	20

The second class of diphenylamine-aldehydes reactions depends on the formation of highly unstable and deliquescent ternary iminium salts (S). These salts may either autoxidise with atmospheric oxygen to give a deeply coloured compound (T) or decompose to give the reactants. The amine and the aldehyde so obtained may autoxidise to give a deeply coloured compound (P) and the corresponding acid via the peroxide free radical respectively. This type of ternary iminium salts are obtained from the reaction of diphenylamine with benzaldehyde O-vanilline, anisaldehyde and salicylaldehyde. To 5 ml (0.05 mole) of benzaldehyde in 250 ml of carbon-tetrachloride was added 4.2 gm (0.025 mole) of diphenylamine. A clear solution was obtained which gives a soft yellow precipitate on adding concentrated hydrochloric acid (0.5 ml) dropwise with continuous shaking. Perchloric acid or sulphuric acid can be used in place of hydrochloric acid. The precipitate so obtained was filtered, washed with carbon tetrachloride and dried at 25°. To 2 ml (0.02 mole) benzaldehyde in 10 ml ethanol was added 2.7 g (0.01 mole) diphenylamine perchlorate. A yellow solution was obtained which turns green on heating (100°) for half an hour. After cooling (0°) a green gummy precipitate was

obtained. The precipitate so obtained was filtered, washed, dried at 30° and then dissolved in acetonitrile-perchloric acid (1 : 1) mixture. From this solution a green product was precipitated by adding water in excess. The product was filtered, washed with water and ethanol and dried.

TLC studies in methanol and chloroform showed that the yellow product consists of a green compound that turns bluish green in air (Rf value zero) and diphenylamine hydrochloride (Rf value 1). The yellow product was dried at 25° for 2 hours and then its X-ray pattern was recorded. The product was found to be crystalline (Table 2, column 1). After 24 hours drying (25°) it turns partly green and partly pale yellow. It was found to be crystalline (Table 2, column 2). After 4 days drying at the same temperature it turns bluish green and found to be poorly crystalline (Table 2, column 3). The relative intensity of the X-ray lines for three phases have been given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—X-RAY DATA OF BENZALDEHYDE-DIPHENYLAMINE HYDROCHLORIC ACID PRODUCT

After 2 hours drying at 25°C	After 24 hours drying at 25°C	After 4 days drying at 25°C		
—	—	7.248	19.8	—
6.505	18.0	6.505	19.8	—
5.675	19.8	5.749	28.8	—
5.466	20.7	5.467	34.2	—
5.063	20.7	5.092	28.8	—
4.480	21.6	4.800	36.0	—
4.111	34.2	4.111	61.2	—
—	—	4.073	57.6	—
3.931	46.8	3.931	100.0	3.931
3.616	23.4	3.616	30.6	—
3.450	25.2	3.477	32.4	—
3.324	19.8	3.348	23.4	3.205
3.162	27.0	3.184	34.2	3.184
3.118	18.0	—	—	—
3.015	18.0	3.035	16.2	—
2.882	19.6	2.882	18.0	2.900
—	—	2.829	10.8	—
2.744	18.0	2.761	25.2	—
—	—	2.712	23.4	2.712
2.696	18.0	2.605	10.8	—
2.605	14.4	2.466	19.0	2.440
2.330	12.6	2.342	12.6	—
2.285	12.6	2.296	10.8	—
—	—	2.274	12.6	—
2.199	10.8	2.105	7.2	—

X-ray data recorded in table 2 are corresponding to diphenylamine hydrochloride (ASTM 5.0326). On the basis of these results it may be concluded that the yellow product is a mixture of non-crystalline ternary iminium salt (S) and crystalline diphenylamine hydrochloride. The yellow ternary iminium salt rapidly oxidizes to green compound (T) and diphenylamine hydrochloride slowly oxidizes to blue compound (P).

For green compound(T) I.R. spectrum by KBr method consists of a strong and broad band from 1637 to 1680 cm^{-1} . N.M.R. spectrum in deuterated dimethylsulphoxide and D_2O on 90 MHz Varian consists of a signal at $\delta=8.94$ ($J=20$ Hz, t, 3 Ph). On treating green solution with zinc dust decolorization occurs. The elemental analysis results are the following for compound (T)

	C	H	N
Found :	84.40	5.75	4.89
Per cent			
Calculated :	83.50	5.40	5.10

The intense colour of the green product is consistent with the large conjugated system of zwitter ionic structure (T). This type of colour stuff has been studied by Acheson *et al*¹¹. Streuli and Averell¹² have remarked, "the Schiff base produced by condensation of an amine with an aldehyde in strong acid solution, can be oxidized by atmospheric oxygen to give a coloured material". Similar opinion has also been given by Feigl¹³.

The colour of the oxidized material is more intense than that of the ternary iminium salt. Thus, it can be used for the sensitive colorimetric detection and determination. The oxidation occurs at a very high rate in dimethylsulfoxide. Thus it seems to be a good analytical reagent.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. Asif-uz-Zaman for facilities and important discussions.

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